

РОССИЙСКАЯ АКАДЕМИЯ НАУК
Южный научный центр

RUSSIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES
Southern Scientific Centre

Кавказский Энтомологический Бюллетень

CAUCASIAN ENTOMOLOGICAL BULLETIN

Том 21. Вып. 2

Vol. 21. Iss. 2

Ростов-на-Дону
2025

Taxonomic and faunistic news on seed-beetles (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae) of the Near East, the Caucasus and some other areas of the Western Palaearctic

© D.G. Kasatkin¹, K.-W. Anton²

¹All-Russian Centre of Plant Quarantine, 20th line, 43/16, Rostov-on-Don 344037 Russia. E-mail: dorcadion@yandex.ru

²Grünewaldstrasse, 13, Emmendingen 79312 Germany. E-mail: bruchitax@gmx.de

Abstract. New data on the distribution and host plants of seed-beetles (Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae) from the Near East, the Caucasus and some other areas of the Western Palaearctic are presented. Two species are firstly recorded for Azerbaijan, three for each Iran and Afghanistan, two for Georgia, one each for Israel, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan. Distribution was clarified for some species. In addition, the images of some rare species are given. Lectotypes for *Bruchus glycyrrhizae* Gyllenhal, 1839 and *Bruchus incipiens* Kolenati, 1858 are designated. The following new synonymy is proposed: *Bruchidius glycyrrhizae* (Gyllenhal, 1839) = *Bruchus incipiens* Kolenati, 1858, **syn. n.**

Key words: Bruchinae, lectotypes, new synonymy, new records, host plants.

Новые данные по таксономии и фаунистике жуков-зерновок (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae) Ближнего Востока, Кавказского региона и некоторых других территорий Западной Палеарктики

© Д.Г. Касаткин¹, К.-В. Антон²

¹Всероссийский центр карантина растений, 20-я линия, 43/16, Ростов-на-Дону 344037 Россия. E-mail: dorcadion@yandex.ru

²Грюневальдштрассе, 13, Эммендинген 79312 Германия. E-mail: bruchitax@gmx.de

Резюме. Представлены новые данные о распространении и кормовых растениях жуков-зерновок (Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae) с Ближнего Востока, Кавказа и некоторых других территорий Западной Палеарктики. Два вида впервые указаны для Азербайджана, по три – для Ирана и Афганистана, два – для Грузии, по одному – для Израиля, Казахстана, Таджикистана и Туркменистана. Для некоторых видов уточнено распространение. Приведены изображения некоторых редких видов. Обозначены лектотипы *Bruchus glycyrrhizae* Gyllenhal, 1839 и *Bruchus incipiens* Kolenati, 1858. Установлена новая синонимия: *Bruchidius glycyrrhizae* (Gyllenhal, 1839) = *Bruchus incipiens* Kolenati, 1858, **syn. n.**

Ключевые слова: Bruchinae, лектотипы, новая синонимия, новые указания, кормовые растения.

New data on the distribution of some species of seed-beetles are presented after examination of materials from different museums, as well as the author's collection. Also, for a several of species, we are clarifying and supplementing the distribution data indicated in the last edition of the catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera [Anton, 2024]. In addition, the study of the type material of *Bruchus incipiens* (Kolenati, 1858) allowed us to establish a new synonymy.

Depositories of examined material:

FSCV – Federal Scientific Center of the East Asia Terrestrial Biodiversity of the Far East Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences (Vladivostok, Russia);

HNHM – Hungarian Natural History Museum (Budapest, Hungary);

NHMB – Naturhistorisches Museum Basel (Switzerland);

NHRS – Naturhistoriska Riksmuseet (Stockholm, Sweden);

NMHD – Natural History Museum of Denmark (Copenhagen, Denmark);

NMPC – National Museum (Prague, Czech Republic);

pcEA – private collection of E.N. Akulov (Krasnoyarsk, Russia);

pcKWA – private collection of K.-W. Anton (Emmendingen, Germany);

pcDK – private collection of D.G. Kasatkin (Rostov-on-Don, Russia);

VNIIKR – collection of All-Russian Plant Quarantine Centre (Moscow, Russia);

SMNS – Staatliches Museum für Naturkunde (Stuttgart, Germany);

KhU – Kharkov State University (Ukraine);

ZIN – Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (St Petersburg, Russia);

ZMMU – Zoological Museum of Moscow University (Moscow, Russia).

Bruchidius holosericeus (Schoenherr, 1832)

Material. 2♂ (VNIIKR), Russia, Dagestan, Derbent Distr., 2.3 km NE Dzhalgan, 42.046°N / 48.265°E, 350 m, 24.05.2021 (K.A. Grebennikov); 1♂, 1♀ (pcDK), same locality, 2.05.2022 (K.A. Grebennikov).

Distribution. This species is distributed in Southern Europe, Transcaucasia, the Near East and Turkmenistan (Kopetdag Mts) [Anton, 2010; Ghahari, Borowiec, 2017]. Anton [2024] listed it for the fauna of Russia as “ST” (= Russia: South European territory). Several specimens

of *B. holosericeus* were collected in the eastern part of the Northern Caucasus.

Bruchidius cinerascens (Gyllenhal, 1833)

Material. Afghanistan. 1♀ (ZIN), upper reaches of Tsangal River, 5–27.06.1972 (O.N. Kabakov).

Tajikistan. 1♀ (ZIN), Sarkoron, Khozrati-sho Mt. Ridge, 1800 m, 10.07.1958 (Lopatin).

Distribution. Widely distributed species. North Africa, Central and Southern Europe, southern Russia (including the North Caucasus), Transcaucasia, the Near East. The first record for Afghanistan and Tajikistan.

Bruchidius richteri Lukjanovitch et Ter-Minassian, 1954

Material. Turkey. 1♀ (HNHM), Yozgat Prov., 10 km N of Yozgat, 10.06.1989 (I. Rozner); 1♂, 6♀ (pcKWA), Karaman Prov., 1 km E of Binbirkilise, 16.06.2004 (K.-W. Anton); 1♂ (pcDK), Niğde Prov., near Darboğaz vill., 3.06.2010 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Iran. 1♀ (NHMB), Mazandaran, Polour – Abali, 2100–2600 m, 17.05.1970 (W. Wittmer, V. Bothmer); 1♂, 2♀ (pcDK), Azerbaijan-e-Qarbi Prov., near Rajan, 37.395448°N / 44.849448°E, 25.05.2014 (D.G. Kasatkin); 2♂ (pcDK), Zanjan Prov., 40 km NE of Bonab, 36.799154°N / 48.73157°E, 9–10.05.2017 (D.G. Kasatkin); 1♀ (pcDK), Alborz Prov., near Gachsar vill., 4–6.06.2023 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Distribution. This species is distributed in Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran [Anton, 2024]. It was recorded for Iran from Qazvin and Tehran [Ghahari, Borowiec, 2017], for Turkey from Sivas [Ekiz, 2022]. Our data significantly expand our knowledge of the range of this species.

Bruchidius ochraceus (Baudi di Selve, 1886)

Material. Turkey. 1♀ (pcKWA), Karaman Prov., Madenşehir, middle of June 1979 (P. Witzgall); 1♀ (ZIN), Erzurum Prov., 8 km S of Oltu, 10.06.1997 (B.A. Korotyaev); 1♂ (pcDK), Tunceli Prov., 25 km SE Ovacik vill., 39.278065°N / 39.451390°E, 23–25.05.2009 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Iran. 1♂ 3♀ (pcDK), Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad Prov., Kūh-e Denā Mt., near Sisaht vill., 30.846959°N / 51.528636°E, 29–31.05.2023 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Distribution. Azerbaijan [Anton, 2024], Armenia and the most countries of the Near East [Anton, 2010]. The species is recorded for Iran for the first time. In addition, according to the recently published checklist of Turkish Bruchinae [Ekiz, 2022], precise data about distribution of *B. ochraceus* in Turkey were not given.

Bruchidius tibialis (Boheman, 1829)

Material. 5 specimens (pcDK), Russia, Krasnodar Region, Adler, 22.04–3.05.2021 (E.A. Khachikov); 10 specimens (pcDK), Russia, Dagestan, Tabasaran Distr., between Khyuryak and Chulat villages, 15 specimens ex Medicago seeds, 3.06.2022 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Notes. The beetles infested seeds of Medicago orbicularis together with *Bruchidius nanus* (Germar, 1824).

Distribution. This species was recorded for Southern Europe, Transcaucasia and the Near East. It was also listed for “Russia: Caucasus” by Ricci and Zampetti [2005] without precise locality data. We examined this species from two different regions of the North Caucasus.

Bruchidius sericatus (Germar, 1823)

Material. Russia. 4 specimens (pcDK), Dagestan, Derbent Distr., 2.3 km NE Dzhalgan, 42.046°N / 48.265°E, 350 m, 24.05.2021 (K.A. Grebennikov).

Azerbaijan. 1♂, 2♀ (pcKWA), Palekesh env., 13–15.05.1992 (A.V. Shamaev); 2♂ (pcKWA), Talysh, 05.1993 (Aleksseeva); 1♂, 2♀ (pcKWA), Quba, 3.05.2003 (R. Rober); 1♂ (pcKWA), Siazan, Qala-Alta, 4.05.2003 (R. Rober).

Distribution. Lukjanovich and Ter-Minassian [1957] recorded this species for the Caucasus without additional information. The species is distributed in Transcaucasian countries according to the catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera [Anton, 2024], and was listed for Russia in the catalogue of Bruchidae [Udayagiri, Wadhi, 1989] without details. This record was not confirmed in any subsequent publications [Kasatkin, 2000; Ghahari, Borowiec, 2017; Anton, 2010, 2024]. Our material is the first documented record of *B. sericatus* in Russia.

Bruchidius mulsanti (Brisout de Barneville, 1863)

Material. Russia. 1 specimen (ZMMU), Krasnodar Region, Gelendzhik env., Markotkh, 30.06.1992 (M.Yu. Savitskiy); 1 specimen (ZIN), Adygea, Perekatnyy vill., near Turgenevskiy bridge, opposite Krasnodar, Kuban River left bank, flood land, 25.05.2010 (B.A. Korotyaev); 1♂, 1♀ (pcDK), Dagestan, 30 km S Derbent, 41.897944°N / 48.505250°E, 30.05–2.06.2022 (D.I. Ryaskin); 1 specimen (pcDK), Dagestan, Tabasaran Distr., between Khyuryak and Chulat vill., 3.06.2022 (D.G. Kasatkin); 2♂ (pcDK), Krasnodar Region, Adler, 05.2021 (E.A. Khachikov).

Azerbaijan. 1♂, 1♀ (pcKWA), Quba, 3.05.2003 (R. Rober).

Iran. 1♀ (pcDK), Gilan Prov., near Bareh-Sara vill., 10.05.2017 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Distribution. The species was listed in the catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera [Anton, 2024] for the south of the European part and the North Caucasus of Russia without specific data. In the “Fauna of the USSR” [Lukjanovich, Ter-Minassian, 1957] this species was listed only for Crimea and Transcaucasia. We examined the material from Krasnodar Region and Dagestan, which confirms the presence of this species in the territory of the Russian Caucasus. In addition, *B. mulsanti* is recorded for Iran for the first time.

Bruchidius glycyrrhizae (Gyllenhal, 1839)

= *Bruchus incipiens* Kolenati, 1858, **syn. n.** (Figs 1–4).

Type material. 1♂, lectotype of *Bruchus glycyrrhizae* Gyllenhal, 1839 (NHRS), hereby designated, “Kytorhinus, Glycyrrhizae, Stev.” (white label, handwritten with black ink).

1♂, lectotype of *Bruchus incipiens* Kolenati, 1858 (NMHD), hereby designated, “Caucasus”, “Kolenati”, “1006” (yellow label), “*Bruchus incipiens* Kol. Kolenati d.”; 1♀, paralectotype (NMHD), “Caucasus”, “Kolenati”, “1007” (yellow label).

Short description of type specimens of *B. incipiens*.

Body black, antennae, legs red-orange, apical part of elytra red, elytral and pronotal disc covered by homogenous dense yellow pubescence, even paler pubescence on scutellum and praescutellar lobe of pronotal disc. Body wide oval, pronotum campaniform, base of 4th elytral striae with well-developed paired tooth, apex of first metatarsomere with spine.

Notes. *Bruchidius incipiens* was listed in the catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera as *incertae sedis* [Anton, 2010, 2024]. Its rather detailed description with data on distribution was given only in the key to seed beetles published in the series “Fauna of the USSR” [Lukyanovich, Ter-Minassian, 1957]. During examination of beetles in NMHD, we found two specimens that fully correspond to the original description of *B. incipiens*, including label data [Kolenati, 1858]. The study of these syntypes showed that the description of the species given by Lukyanovich

Figs 1–4. Lectotype and paralectotype of *Bruchus incipiens*.

1–2 – male, lectotype, habitus: 1 – frontal view, 2 – dorsal view; 3 – female, paralectotype, habitus, dorsal view; 4 – labels.

Рис. 1–4. Лектотип и паралектотип *Bruchus incipiens*.

1–2 – самец, лектотип, габитус: 1 – вид спереди, 2 – вид сверху; 3 – самка, паралектотип, габитус, вид сверху; 4 – этикетки.

and Ter-Minasyan [1957] does not correspond to the specimens of the type series. As to the *Bruchidius* key and the description of species, both authors pointed to black antennae with red basal antennomeres, and to the first metatarsomere without apical spine.

Based on the studied types, the following synonymy is established: *Bruchidius glycyrrhizae* (Gyllenhal, 1839) = *Bruchus incipiens* Kolenati, 1858, **syn. n.**

Bruchidius spathopus Iablokoff-Khnzorian, 1960
(Fig. 5)

Material. Azerbaijan. 1♂ (ZIN), Nakhichevan, 5–8 km N Shakhbuz vill., 16.05.1988 (B.A. Korotyayev).

Iran. 1♂ (pcDK), Kurdistan Prov., Khusheh Darreh, 21–22.05.2023 (D.G. Kasatkin); 1♂ (pcDK), Kurdistan Prov., near Gawilleh, 4–5.06.2025 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Distribution. Hitherto listed for Armenia and Iran (Qazvin) [Ghahari, Borowiec, 2017; Anton, 2024]; first record for Azerbaijan.

Bruchidius varipes (Boheman, 1839)

Type material. 1♂, syntype of *Bruchidius bagdasarjani* Lukjanovitch et Ter-Minassian, 1954 (junior synonym) (ZIN), Armenia, Kanakir, 31.05.1938, (Bagdasarjan).

1♂, holotype of *Bruchidius lukjanovitschi* Ter-Minassian, 1969 (junior synonym) (ZIN), «Азербайджанская ССР, Зувантский район, 1 IX 1937» (Azerbaijan SSR, Zuvant District).

Material. Russia. 1♂ (ZIN), Krasnodar Region, 16 km N Novorossiysk, steppe on the pass, 6.05.1988 (B.A. Korotyayev).

Armenia. 1♂ (pcKWA), Sevan Lake, 5 km S of Sevan, 1950 m, 6.06.1980 (J. Papp); 1♀ (pcKWA), Sevan, 2000 m, 4.07.1989 (A. Pütz); Azerbaijan. 1♂, 1♀ (pcKWA, SMNS), Lerik, Zuvant, Gosmolian, 1300 m, 10–12.06.1996 (W. Schawaller).

Distribution. Eastern Europe, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran, Turkey [Anton, 2024]. It was listed for Russia from the south of the European part and Ural [Anton, 2024]. Last records are based on the labels of junior synonyms: *Bruchus forticornis* (Motschulsky, 1874) and *B. aestuosus* (Motschulsky, 1874). To date, we found only one specimen of this species known from the territory of Russia with exact locality data, which originates from the North-Western Caucasus.

Bruchidius lucifugus (Boheman, 1833)

Material. Georgia. 1♂ 1♀, (pcDK), Akhaltsikhe Distr., Dzveli vill., 15–16.06.2013 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Afghanistan. 1♂ (ZIN), Nurestan, W Waygal, 2200 m, 7.07.1972 (O.N. Kabakov).

Distribution. Southern Russia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Turkey [Anton, 2024]. First records for Georgia and Afghanistan.

Bruchidius sivasensis Zampetti, 1984
(Fig. 6)

Material. Armenia. 1♂, 2♀ (pcKWA, NMPC), Garni, Gokht, valley of Azat River, 1500 m, 29.05.1988 (J. Strejcek); 1♂ (NMPC), same data but 1600 m, 12.06.1988 (Z. Jindra).

Azerbaijan. 1♂ (pcKWA), Talysh, Zuvant, 1600–1700 m, 29.05.2000 (Andreeva).

Iran. 1♂ (pcDK), Lorestan Prov., near Azna vill., 33.279639°N / 49.499288°E, 16–17.05.2017 (D.G. Kasatkin); 1♂ (pcDK), Kurdistan Prov., near Gewelle (Gavileh) vill., 35.707607°N / 46.37848°E, 19.05.2017 (D.G. Kasatkin); 10 specimens (pcDK, VNIKR), Kurdistan Prov., Daraki vill., 35.317733°N / 46.20988°E, 1750–2055 m, 6–7.06.2025 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Distribution. According to the previous authors this species is distributed in Turkey, Armenia, Azerbaijan and Iran [Anton, 2010, 2024; Ghahari, Borowiec, 2017]. In Iran, this species was recorded only from Kuhgiluyeh and Boyerahmad Province [Ghahari, Borowiec 2017]. According to our materials, *B. sivasensis* is widespread in Iran.

Bruchidius khnzoriani Karapetjan, 1976
(Figs 7–10)

Material. 1♂ (pcDK), Iran, Gilan Prov., near Bareh-Sara vill., 36.74955°N / 49.720965°E, 8.05.2017 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Distribution. This species was hitherto known from Armenia only [Karapetyan, 1985]; the first record for Iran. Mentioned above male is conspecific to the holotype of *B. khnzoriani*, which was examined by a photograph.

Bruchidius poecilus (Germar, 1823)

Material. 1♂ (ZIN), Turkmenistan, Syunt mount, 1600 m, 3.05.1971 (G.S. Medvedev); 1♀ (ZIN), Turkmenistan, Khasardag mount, 27.05.1974 (G.S. Medvedev); 2 specimens (ZIN), SW Turkmenistan, W Kopetdag, near Karakala mount, 12.04.1991 (V.N. Prasolov); 1 specimen (ZIN), S Turkmenistan, Kyzyl-Atrek, on light, 19.04.1991 (V.N. Prasolov).

Distribution. Widely distributed in Mediterranean region and the Near East. The first record for Central Asia and Turkmenistan.

Bruchidius marginalis (Fabricius, 1776)

Material. 1 specimen (pcEA), Russia, Krasnoyarsk Region, near Krasnoyarsk, “Stolby” State Reserve, Chyortov palets, swept on steppe slope, 22.06.2018 (E.N. Akulov); more than 30 specimens (VNIKR), Russia, Dagestan, Verkhniy Gunib, 5.06.2022, reared 08.2022 from *Astragalus buschiorum* (D.G. Kasatkin).

Distribution. According previous publications, it is distributed in Europe, the Northern Caucasus, Transcaucasia and Turkey [Lukyanovich, Ter-Minasyan, 1957; Kasatkin, 2000; Anton, 2010, 2024]. Recently [Lopatina, Lukyantsev, 2023] this species was recorded for Siberia (Russia, Khakassia, Ustinkino village). We examined one specimen collected much further east in Krasnoyarsk environs. Also, we registered a new host plant for this species: the large series of *B. marginalis* were reared from seeds of *Astragalus buschiorum* Galushko, 1970.

Acanthoscelides pallidipennis (Motschulsky, 1874)

Material. 1♀ (pcDK), Georgia, Tbilisi, 13.06.2013 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Distribution. The widespread invasive species, whose larvae develop in seeds of *Amorpha fruticosa* L. In Transcaucasia, *A. pallidipennis* occurs in Armenia and Azerbaijan [Anton, 2010, 2024] and is recorded here for Georgia for the first time.

Bruchus nikdeli Delobel et Sadeghi, 2014

Material. 3♀, 4♂ (ZIN), Azerbaijan, Nakhichevan, Shakhbuz Distr., between Ghansor and Makhmudoba villages, 1500–2000 m, 19.05.1988 (B.A. Korotyayev, G.E. Davidian).

Distribution. This species was described from northern Iran (Sakhand); later it was recorded from northeastern Turkey [Melek, Anton, 2022]. The first record for Azerbaijan.

Figs 5–10. Species of the genus *Bruchidius*, general view and details of structure.
 5 – *B. spathopus*; 6 – *B. sivasensis*; 7–10 – *B. khnzoriani*. 5–7 – habitus; 8–10 – male genitalia: 8 – median lobe, 9 – lateral lobes, 10 – microsculpture of lateral lobes.

Рис. 5–10. Виды рода *Bruchidius*, общий вид и детали строения.
 5 – *B. spathopus*; 6 – *B. sivasensis*; 7–10 – *B. khnzoriani*. 5–7 – внешний вид; 8–10 – гениталии самца: 8 – пенис, 9 – парамеры, 10 – микроскульптура парамер.

Figs 11–18. Species of the genus *Bruchus*, general view and details of structure.
 11–14 – *B. tetragonus*; 15–18 – *B. barimani*. 11, 12, 15 – habitus: 11, 15 – male, 12 – female; 13–14, 16–18 – males genitalia: 13, 16 – median lobe, 14, 17 – lateral lobe, 18 – VIII inner abdominal segment (a – tergite, b – sternite).
 Рис. 11–18. Виды рода *Bruchus*, общий вид и детали строения.
 11–14 – *B. tetragonus*; 15–18 – *B. barimani*. 11, 12, 15 – внешний вид: 11, 15 – самец, 12 – самка; 13–14, 16–18 – гениталии самцов: 13, 16 – пенис, 14, 17 – парамеры, 18 – внутренний брюшной сегмент VIII (а – тергит, б – стернит).

Bruchus tetragonus (Baudi di Selve, 1886)
(Figs 11–14)

Material. 1♀ (pcKWA), Turkey, Gaziantep Prov., 20 km W of Kilis, 27.04.1970 (K. Warncke); 1♀, 1♂ (pcDK), Turkey, Mush Prov., above Varto, 17.05.2009 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Distribution. A rare species known only from several localities in Turkey and Syria, never been imaged. According to Ekiz [2022], this species was registered in Diyarbakır, Kahramanmaraş, Mardin and Siirt provinces of Turkey. We add Gaziantep and Mush provinces to its distribution.

Bruchus barimani Delobel et Sadeghi, 2014
(Figs 15–18)

Material. 1♀ (pcDK), Iran, Tehran Prov., ca. 4.5 km NW of Shemshak City, 36.030123°N / 51.448141°E, 2861 m, mountains, subalpine belt, 2.07.2019 (A.S. Prosvirov); 3♂, 4♀ (pcDK), Iran, Alborz Prov., near Gachsar vill., 4–6.06.2023 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Distribution. The species was known only from the type series from Mazandaran, Iran (near Amol). We have material from Tehran and Alborz provinces and obviously this species is distributed in all Central Alborz.

Stator limbatus (Horn, 1873)

Material. 1♀ (KhU), Israel, Poleg Nature Reserve, 32.264448°N / 34.835051°E, 20.01.2015 (A.I. Slutsky); 1♂ (KhU), Israel, Shavei Zion, 32.987001°N / 35.082389°E, 10.04.2018 (A.I. Slutsky).

Distribution. *Stator limbatus* originates from the New World and it was introduced to the Middle East and Mediterranean region. It was hitherto recorded from Cyprus [Demetriou et al., 2022], Sardinia and Corsica [Cocco et al., 2021], the United Arab Emirates, Yemen, Oman and Iran [Anton, 2010, 2024; Boroumand, 2010; Delobel, 2011]. The species is recorded for Israel for the first time.

Acanthobruchidius spiniger (Baudi di Selve, 1886)

Material. Portugal. 1♂ (ZIN), "Lusitania", "*Bruchus histrio* Schh.", "Кол. Соляского" (Solsky collection).

Iran. 1♂, 1♀ (pcDK), Kurdistan Prov., near Talijar vill., 23.05.2023 (D.G. Kasatkin); 1♂ (pcDK), Kurdistan Prov., near Gaville, 4–5.06.2025 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Distribution. This species was listed for the Near East and East Mediterranean (Lesbos, Rhodes) [Anton, 2024]. One specimen from Iberian Peninsula is deposited in ZIN, but this record needs confirmation in modern fauna. The species was recorded for Iran without localities [Ghahari, Borowiec, 2017]. According to our material it occurs at least in Kurdistan Province.

Conicobruchus kashmiricus (Pic, 1929)

Material. 1♀ (ZIN), Afghanistan, Nurestan, SW Čapa-Dara, 1300 m, 20.06.1971 (O.N. Kabakov); 1♀ (ZIN), Afghanistan, Konar, W Barikot, 2000 m, 21.07.1972 (O.N. Kabakov).

Distribution. This species was listed for Pakistan, North India and Nepal [Anton, 2010, 2024]. The first record for Afghanistan.

Conicobruchus steveni (Gyllenhal, 1839)

Material. 2♂, 1♀ (pcDK), Iran, Alborz Prov., near Gachsar vill., 4–6.06.2023 (D.G. Kasatkin).

Distribution. According previous authors, this species was recorded from "N. Iran" without precisions data [Lukjanovitch, Ter-Minassian, 1957; Ghahari, Borowiec, 2017; Anton, 2024]. We collected some specimens in Alborz Province and confirm the presence it in Iranian fauna.

Amblycerus robiniae (Fabricius, 1781)

Material. 1♂ (FSCV), Russia, Primorskiy Region, Terney settl., from *Gymnocladus dioicus* seeds, 11.2018 (S. Bondarchuk).

Distribution. This invasive species was reported for the Eurasian fauna firstly in 2018, beetles were collected in Romania [Rădac et al., 2021]. A previous record was related with beetles obtained from imported seeds [Merkl, 2001]. One mentioned in the material male was reared from seed of *Gymnocladus dioicus* (L.) K. Koch in the Russian Far East, but these seeds were collected in Kiev (Ukraine) (M.E. Sergeev, personal communication, 2022). Thus, we can expect *A. robiniae* being present in Ukraine.

Spermophagus rufipes Ter-Minassian, 1975

Material. 1♂ (ZIN), SE Kazakhstan, hunting farm "Mynbulak", Poyushchiy barkhan, 14.05.1990 (V.N. Prasolov).

Distribution. Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia [Anton, 2024]. This species is recorded for Kazakhstan for the first time.

Acknowledgements

The authors cordially thank Dr B.A. Korotyayev (ZIN) for the provided museum's collection, Dr K.A. Grebennikov (Moscow, Russia), Mr D.I. Ryaskin (Voronezh, Russia), Mr E.N. Akulov (Krasnoyarsk, Russia), Mr A.I. Slutsky (Kharkov, Ukraine) for provided material, Dr M.Yu. Kalashian and Dr T.L. Ghrejjyan (Yerevan, Armenia) for photographs of some type specimens. The authors thank the reviewers for valuable comments.

This work was supported by the state project 081-00006-25-00 for D.G. Kasatkin.

References

- Anton K.-W. 2010. Family Bruchinae Latreille, 1802. In: Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera. Chrysomeloidea. Vol. 6. Stenstrup: Apollo Books: 62–64, 339–353.
- Anton K.-W. 2024. Subfamily Bruchinae Latreille, 1802. In: Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera. Chrysomelidae. Vol. 6/2/1. Updated and revised second edition. Leiden – Boston: Brill: 3–24, 176–206.
- Boroumand H. 2010. The first report of the genus and species of the seed beetle, *Stator limbatus* (Col.: Bruchidae), from Iran. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*. 29(2): 119–120.
- Cocco A., Brundu G., Berquier C., Andrei-Ruiz M.C., Pusceddu M., Porceddu M., Podda L., Satta A., Petit Y., Floris I. 2021. Establishment and new hosts of the non-native seed beetle *Stator limbatus* (Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae, Bruchinae) on acacias in Europe. *Neo Biota*. 70: 167–192. DOI: 10.3897/neobiota.70.70441
- Delobel A. 2011. Order Coleoptera, family Chrysomelidae, Subfamily Bruchinae. In: Arthropod fauna of the UAE. Volume 4. Abu Dhabi: Dar Al Ummah: 274–285.
- Demetriou J., Kakiopoulos G., Hava J., Martinou A.F., Delobel A. 2022. First record of the alien seed beetle *Stator limbatus* (Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae, Bruchinae) from Cyprus. *Travaux du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle "Grigore Antipa"*. 65(1): 37–43. DOI: 10.3897/travaux.64.e81350
- Ghahari H., Borowiec L. 2017. A checklist of seed-beetles (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae) from Iran. *Zootaxa*. 4268(2): 215–237. DOI: 10.11646/zootaxa.4268.2.3

- Ekiz A.N. 2022. Annotated checklist of the seed beetles (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae) of Turkey. *Acta Entomologica Serbica*. 27(2): 1–23. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7225312
- Karapetyan A.P. 1985. Fauna Armiyanskoy SSR, Nasekomye, Zhestkokrylye. Zernovki (Bruchidae) [Fauna of the Armenian SSR. Insecta, Coleopterans. Seed-beetles (Bruchidae)]. Yerevan: Academy of Sciences of the Armenian SSR. 171 p. (in Russian).
- Kasatkin D.G. 2000. Materials on studying the fauna of Bruchidae (Coleoptera) from the south of the European part of Russia and the Northern Caucasus. *Izvestiya Khar'kovskogo entomologicheskogo obshchestva*. 8(1): 95–106 (in Russian).
- Kolenati F. 1858. Meletemata Entomologica. Fascicule VIIIa. *Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou*. 31(1): 102–184, 4 pls.
- Lopatina S.V., Lukyantsev S.V. 2023. *Bruchidius marginalis* (Fabricius, 1776) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae) – a species new to the Republic of Khakassia (Russia). *Acta Biologica Sibirica*. 9: 597–603. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8333434
- Lukjanovich F.K., Ter-Minassian M.E. 1957. Fauna SSSR. Zhestkokrylye. Tom XXIV, vyp. 1. Zhuki-zernovki (Bruchidae) [Fauna of the USSR. Coleoptera. Vol. 24, Issue 1. Seed-beetles (Bruchidae)]. Moscow, Leningrad: Academy of Sciences of the USSR. 208 p. (in Russian).
- Melek G.G., Anton K.-W. 2022. First description of the female of *Bruchus nikdeli* Delobel and Sadeghi (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae) and first record from Turkey. *The Coleopterists Bulletin*. 76(1): 39–44. DOI: 10.1649/0010-065X-76.1.39
- Merkl O. 2001. Rovarküldöttek. *Élővilág*. 10: 12–17.
- Rădac I.-A., Mancu C.O., Pintilioaie A.-M. 2021. *Amblycerus robiniae* (Fabricius, 1781) (Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae), an alien species established in Europe. *BiolInvasions Records*. 10(1): 57–64. DOI: 10.3391/bir.2021.10.1.07
- Ricci M.E., Zampetti M. 2005. Contributo alla conoscenza dei bruchidi dell'Europa (Coleoptera, Bruchidae). *Entomologica, Bari*. 39: 121–167.
- Udayagiri S., Wadhi S.R. 1989. Catalog of Bruchidae. *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute*. 45: 1–301.

Received / Поступила: 3.09.2025

Accepted / Принята: 24.11.2025

Published online / Опубликовано онлайн: 30.12.2025